

THE MAIN ASPECTS OF CULTURE BUMP AND ITS IMPORTANT ROLE

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"Culture is the name for what people are interested in, their thoughts, their models, the books they read and the speeches they hear.

Walter Lippmann

ABSTRACT: *The impact of a cultural difference on perceptions is largely explained by the culture bump idea. The discovery of the connection between the two distinctions and the resulting impression gave rise to the culture bump stages, a particular method for recognizing and utilizing cultural differences.*

KEY WORDS: *cultural differences, culture bump, emotional component, culture-free conversation.*

INTRODUCTION

When one adopts a "culture bump" mindset, they can see cultural differences not as issues that need to be resolved but rather as chances to understand others and themselves better. Bumps in Culture and Perceptions A "cultural difference" is the definition given to the culture bump (Archer, 1991). A person experiences this phenomenon when they interact with someone from a different culture when they expect one person to behave a certain way in a given setting, but they end up with someone other. According to Archer (1991), expectations are the standards of "normal behavior as learned in one's own culture." This idea proposes that experiencing a cultural shock has several implications. These include the construction of a perception, an emotional reaction, and a knowledge paradox that prompts an information search. The fundamental idea behind the cultural bump theory is that people experience culture bumps whether or not they are aware of

them. People frequently don't even realize they have culture bumps; instead, they just feel disconnected, which is a combination of their emotional and rational selves that they are rarely aware of. Global issues aren't always bad; they're just problems that need to be addressed. In this regard, issues relating to culture bump include the problems we face locally, such as the increased number of foreign residents, and we discuss issues like the issues that arise from population growth. We can truly see that any of us can be susceptible to any of the isms thanks to the cultural bump technique. Whatever the cause, classism, racism, islamophobia, or sexism, gender, race, or religion all combine to influence how people relate with different cultures. This is also true of socioeconomic demographics. Certain approaches truly require knowing how to connect as well as how to appreciate differences. Due to the fact that a lack of connection is the primary issue. It is simple to turn away and stop bothering yourself with unfamiliar people, cultures, locations, or events when you don't understand them or don't know how to connect with them.

In line with the explanation provided by Archer and Nickson (2012), a Culture Bump occurs when someone expects "a particular behavior" in a specific scenario and runs across differences when engaging with people from different cultures. "Normal behavior as learned in one's own culture" is referred to as a particular behavior (Archer, 1991). Intercultural communication is hampered by these kinds of disparities. A feeling of alienation is all that culture bumps feel like, and most individuals are unaware that they even exist. Even those with extensive cross-cultural experience, like EFL teachers, can respond negatively in certain situations. Archer and Nickson (2012) have identified two aspects of Culture Bump's impact:

- The Emotional Component: Culture bumps can have a good or negative impact on a person's emotional faculty depending on whether they perceive the cultural difference favorably or unfavorably, or they can remain neutral

when no strong emotions are felt. It may vary from time to time, depending on the circumstances.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The following steps are a structured way to replicate a culture-free conversation about any cultural difference at any time:

- Step 1: Identify the culture bump;
- Step 2: Describe the behavior of the Other(s);
- Step 3: Describe your own behavior;
- Step 4: List your feelings during the incident;
- Step 5: Extrapolate the general situation out of the particular incident.
- Step 6: Explain the conduct in that global scenario that you would exhibit yourself or that you would anticipate from a member of your own culture
- .Step 7: When it happens in your own culture or when you engage in that typical conduct, pinpoint and label the precise underlying "human" characteristic that you attribute to it.
- Step 8: Consider how people from the other culture would be able to tell when someone possesses or lacks that "human" quality. Consider the exact standards by which you (or someone from that culture) may judge whether or not that trait exists in their culture.

Figure 26.2 Diagram of a Culture-Bound Interaction

It is the main diagram of Culture-Bound Interaction which is utilized in cross-culture communication. By the help of this diagram we can notice that these 5 steps includes a chain for connection of cultures. Culture bump refers to the experience of being confronted with a new and different culture, which may lead to feelings of confusion, disorientation, and frustration. It occurs when individuals encounter beliefs, values, customs, and communication styles that are unfamiliar to them. Understanding the main aspects of culture bump and recognizing its important role can help individuals navigate and adapt to new cultural experiences.

1. **Awareness of Cultural Differences:** Culture bump highlights the importance of being aware of and acknowledging cultural differences. It helps individuals recognize that their own cultural lens may differ from others, promoting cultural understanding and acceptance.
2. **Emotional Reaction:** Culture bump often elicits emotional reactions such as confusion, frustration, or even amusement. These reactions signify the clash between expectations and the reality of a new culture, leading to a heightened awareness of cultural differences.
3. **Communication Challenges:** Language barriers, non-verbal cues, and communication styles that differ from one's own may cause misunderstandings in cross-cultural interactions. Culture bump emphasizes the need for effective communication skills and adapting to different cultural norms of communication.
4. **Increased Self-Awareness:** Culture bump fosters introspection and self-reflection. It encourages individuals to examine their own cultural assumptions and biases, helping them develop self-awareness and a deeper understanding of their own culture.
5. **Learning Opportunity:** Culture bump provides a valuable learning opportunity for individuals to expand their cultural knowledge, enhance intercultural competence, and develop empathy towards others. It allows individuals to challenge their preconceived notions and broaden their perspectives.
6. **Adaptation and Integration:** Culture bump challenges individuals to adapt to new cultural environments and integrate into unfamiliar social and professional settings. It emphasizes the importance of being open-minded, flexible, and willing to learn from others.

Indeed, the important role of culture bump lies in fostering cultural intelligence, developing intercultural competence, and promoting empathy and understanding across cultures. It prepares individuals for the challenges of living

and interacting in multicultural environments, ultimately bridging cultural gaps and promoting global harmony.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a carefully choreographed process moves from the culture bump to culture-specific information to underlying universality. This is how culture bump training basically integrates the culture bump as a concept and a method into an intercultural communication workshop framework. The construction of a training methodology that complies with Abdallah-Preteille's (2006) request to "learn to see to hear to be mindful of other people" (p. 476), is made possible by the cultural bump theory, which serves as a model for a hermeneutical instructional approach. This methodical approach to teaching cultural awareness offers a structured means of accessing the learner's life experience in all of its singularity and applying a particular procedure to examine it. The question of whether we learn more about ourselves or about others is ignored by this methodology, which emerged from the cultural bump idea. Rather, the investigation is more about learning how to study with the training for cultural knowledge. Culture bump training is more about the talks we engage with each other in which we define existential topics together and find common ground than it is about subject matter. "This connection ultimately allows students to understand the concept of cultural relativism at a conscious, personal level," writes Archer et al. (2016). A communicative breakdown will occur if an EFL classroom, or any language classroom for that matter, is unable to create an equilibrium between the target culture and the native one. This equilibrium will be achieved through stereotyping the people and behaviors of the target culture. A culture bump refers to the discomfort or confusion experienced when encountering a new culture or unfamiliar customs, values, and behaviors. It can happen when someone travels to a foreign country, meets people from different backgrounds, or interacts with individuals who have different beliefs and practices. Culture bumps can lead to misunderstandings, miscommunication, and even conflict when people

are not aware or accepting of cultural differences. However, they can also provide an opportunity for personal growth, learning, and building bridges between different cultures.

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